

MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of improving the methodology for developing the creative competence of future primary school teachers. The study highlights the theoretical and practical foundations of the development of the creative competence of primary school teachers, the structural components of the formation of creative competence, as well as suggestions for improving the methodology of its development. The methodology proposed in the article is of practical importance for the development of creative competence in the field of primary education.*

Keywords: *primary school teachers, creative competence, improvement mechanisms, development methodology.*

Main part:

The main mechanisms of the process of developing the creative competence of elementary school teachers are discussed. To accomplish this, the author clearly defines the methods, technologies, forms, and techniques for developing and improving this competence.

The mechanisms for improving the methodology for developing the creative competence of primary school teachers are as follows:

1. Developing the creative qualities of teacher's personality.
2. Developing teachers' competencies in organizing creative activities.
3. Developing teachers' competencies in evaluating and analyzing creative activities.
4. Developing teachers' creative thinking.
5. Developing teachers' competencies in practical implementation and realization of experiences.

According to the analysis of sources, competence is considered to be a set of interrelated personal qualities established in relation to a certain range of objects and processes, necessary for qualitative and effective action towards them.

Competence is the possession of necessary competences by an individual, including their personal attitude and being a subject of activity. Being proficient, the ability to mobilize acquired knowledge and experience in a specific situation signify competence.

Professionalism is the achievement of high standards in implementing several aspects of pedagogical work (activity, communication, teacher's personality).

The concept of professionalism is used in a very broad sense, and it is understood as a special property of people for the systematic, efficient, and reliable performance of complex activities in various conditions. To acquire professional skills, you need relevant abilities, desire, and character, constant learning, and readiness to improve your skills. Professional competence is a necessary component of person's professionalism.

When defining teacher's creative competence, it is a multifaceted phenomenon that encompasses a system of teacher's theoretical knowledge and methods of applying them in specific pedagogical situations, teacher's value orientations, as well as integral indicators of their culture.

A competent teacher embodies a high level of professional, pedagogical, psychological, and social qualities. Thus, teacher's creative competence combines creative - that is, special, methodological, psychological and pedagogical - training, creativity (in relationships, the educational process itself, optimal use of tools, techniques, teaching methods) and artistry (acting and public speaking skills).

Today, it is becoming clear that it is impossible to "add up" ordinary knowledge to create a qualified specialist. A new image of the teacher has emerged: a researcher, an instructor, a consultant, and a project manager. Therefore, teachers need to continually improve their creative competence from year to year and from lesson to lesson.

What mechanisms are necessary to organize the activities of future elementary school teachers, aimed at enhancing the creative competence of future teachers based on a creative approach?

Stage 1. Determining the level of teacher's creative competence: diagnostics, testing.

Stage 2. Developing recommendations for further enhancing the creative competence of teachers.

Stage 3. Identifying ways to enhance creative competence.

The mechanisms for developing teacher's creative competence include:

Professional development courses, including distance learning, etc. Currently, the diversity of topics in this form of professional development allows teachers to choose courses that interest them and enhance their professionalism.

Teachers' master classes, group work, creative groups, workshops, subject decades, analysis of conducted tests, and events of various levels. This work, of course, helps to raise the professional level of the teacher.

Active participation in teachers' councils, seminars, conferences.

The value of teachers' meetings, seminars, methodological days, and open lesson weeks is primarily reflected in the preparatory work. To prepare an open lesson or speech, it is sometimes necessary to review several materials, analyze the experience of teachers, compare it with others' experiences, and update and supplement methodological-pedagogical experience. Of course, for some, this may seem like unnecessary experiences and worries, but the work done contributes to increasing creative competence, and words of gratitude from students and colleagues serve as inspiration.

Participation in various competitions. This always provides additional experience and serves as an incentive for development and improvement. The teacher analyzes their educational activities and distinguishes between positive and negative aspects.

Participation in scientific research, creation of their own publications.

Generalizing and Disseminating Experience;

Teacher Certification;

Creative Reporting;

The Use Of Modern methods, forms, types, teaching aids, and new technologies.

Analyzing teacher's activities or observing lessons. A modern teacher should reflect on his or her activities. This involves revisiting their past work and answering the following questions:

"What have I done?", "What have I achieved, and what makes me happy about it?", "What failures have I encountered, and what are the causes of my difficulties?", and finally: "What should I have done to avoid making mistakes?".

Self-education (all of the above includes this self-education). Self-education of young teachers is a necessary condition for their creative activity. Society always places the highest demands on teachers.

To teach others, a teacher needs to know more than others. A teacher must not only know his or her subject and its teaching methodology but also possess knowledge in related scientific fields, various spheres of public life, and be familiar with modern politics, economics, and other areas. The teacher must constantly learn, as students' knowledge increases each year, and their understanding of the world deepens and even changes.

Creative competence and development issues in higher education institutions are current practices for future primary school teachers who manage them creatively. In particular, they want to understand the content and essence of creative education when planning their subject.

Today, one of the main challenges in modern education is providing creative, objective, and innovative support to future teachers in their creative and personal development, as well as preparing creative thinkers for professional work.

Identifying the best teaching methods involves activities that develop creative competence, creativity, non-standard thinking and behavior, decision-making skills, understanding, and experience.

Therefore, in today's conditions, the main task of higher education is to prepare future teachers to work with various educational programs, textbooks, and institutions.

The creative self-expression of future primary school teachers reflects person's desire for freedom and the need for self-realization through communication with free individuals.

Organizing detailed information about the learning process is effective in filling and enhancing various positions. The social environment and changes in creating new things in the external and internal world of the project.

Creative self-expression demonstrates the ability of future primary school teachers to transition from simple work to perfect work, to go beyond work, and work with a strong work ethic. Creative self-expression is not about expressing oneself for others, but rather the growth of future teachers, their personal knowledge, understanding, and ability to work. By changing their work and self-development, they can become a person who expresses their true self.

Creative competence is a professional activity specific to a field. The content of professional competence in a specific field is determined by the functions of the position, and the nature and content of the professional tasks that need to be addressed. Specialist's creative abilities ensure the productivity and effectiveness of their professional activities, professional success, and level of self-realization. These develop depending on their level of professional education, creatively important personal qualities, and creative experience.

Implementing a long-term strategy for the development of education, upbringing, and the social sphere in our country requires introducing innovations based on modern information and communication technologies into the educational process. The success of this depends on future teacher's initiative, creative thinking, and ability to find non-standard solutions.

Self-education is carried out through the following measures:

- watching television programs, reading the press;

- familiarization with pedagogical and methodological literature;
- regular use of information from the Internet;
- participation in seminars, trainings, conferences, and colleagues' lessons;
- systematic professional development;
- studying modern psychological and pedagogical methods;
- systematic demonstration of one's pedagogical experience.

By utilizing all means and mechanisms of development to achieve creative competence based on a creative approach, we have the opportunity to shape an individual who is:

curious, interested, and actively aware of the world;

able to learn and organize his or her own activities;

respectful and accepting of family and societal values, as well as the history and culture of each nation;

friendly, able to listen to and hear partners, respecting one's own and others' opinions;

ready to act independently and take responsibility for actions.

As A. Disterweg said, "Just as no one can give to another what they do not have themselves, no one who is not developed, educated, and cultured can develop, educate, and teach others. Only by working on one's own upbringing and education can one become capable of teaching and educating".

Summary

The application of improvement mechanisms for developing the creative competence of elementary school teachers yields effective results. These mechanisms are implemented through the improvement of teacher's personality, competencies in conducting creative activities, evaluation and analysis, development of thinking, and practical application of experience.

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